

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THROMBOCYTOPENIA AND PREECLAMPSIA IN WOMEN IN LABOR

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Background and objective

Thrombocytopenia, which is characterized by a platelet count of less than $150 \times 10^9/L$, is demonstrated to be the second most frequent cause of hematological abnormalities during pregnancy, behind anemia. A recent study found a clear correlation between severe thrombocytopenia and several ailments. Comparing the platelet counts of individuals with preeclampsia with those in a control group of healthy, age-matched adults during delivery was the primary objective of the current investigation. This study aimed to elucidate potential differences in platelet counts during delivery, particularly with regard to preeclampsia, a condition characterized by high blood pressure and often linked to decreased platelet counts.

Methods

In this particular case-control investigation, a comparison was made regarding thrombocytopenia between 50 individuals diagnosed with preeclampsia and 60 healthy controls of similar age. The classification of thrombocytopenia in this research encompassed four categories:

1. standard range ($150-400 \times 10^9/L$).
2. ($100-149 \times 10^9/L$) is modest.
3. mild ($50-99 \times 10^9/L$).
4. severe (less than $50 \times 10^9/L$).

Result:

The study's findings demonstrated that the patients' and controls' general information was the same. With a statistically significant P-value of less than 0.0001, the platelet count of preeclampsia patients was found to be substantially lower (73.58 ± 26.05) than that of the control group (262.05 ± 81.01). In addition, the cases exhibited greater urine protein ($P < 0.0001$) and considerably lower levels of bilirubin ($P < 0.0001$) and serum creatinine ($P = 0.002$) as compared to the controls. Preeclampsia also raised the likelihood of problems from antepartum hemorrhage (67.3% vs. 18.6%), emergency cesarean sections (65.5% vs. 11.9%), development of different hypertensive diseases throughout pregnancy (60.0% vs. 35.6%), and hospitalizations to the neonatal intensive care unit.

Conclusion

The current research findings revealed a significant difference in platelet count between preeclamptic patients and non-pre-eclamptic individuals, with the former exhibiting lower platelet levels. Moreover, the preeclamptic group demonstrated a higher incidence of obstetrical complications compared to the non-preeclamptic group. These findings highlight the potential impact of preeclampsia on platelet count and obstetrical outcomes in pregnant women.

Introduction:

Thrombocytopenia, or low platelet counts, is a condition that is frequently recognized as the second most significant cause causing blood issues during pregnancy, behind anemia. Gestational thrombocytopenia is a disease that is common during pregnancy and is thought to impact 7–12% of pregnancies. Severe thrombocytopenia can lead to serious issues that need to be monitored and treated medically, for both the mother and the fetus. Since thrombocytopenia is one of the main causes of maternal mortality and morbidity, it is a serious worldwide health problem. Research indicates that women with thrombocytopenia are at increased risk of dying from a range of complications that occur during and after pregnancy as well as after giving birth, such as severe bleeding, infections (which are common after giving birth), preeclampsia and eclampsia, issues associated with the delivery process, and unsafe abortion practices. Surprisingly, a significant portion of these problems are preventable or effectively managed with early intervention. Importantly, even though many of these issues may have existed before to conception, they frequently worsen throughout the gestational period, underscoring the significance of preventive healthcare measures for women of reproductive age. Remarkably, a staggering 75% of global maternal deaths are related to the many issues associated with thrombocytopenia. This graph highlights how important it is for healthcare providers to prioritize treating pregnant women with thrombocytopenia as soon as possible to minimize risks and improve outcomes for expecting moms. By implementing comprehensive treatment programs that address thrombocytopenia-related issues, healthcare systems can considerably lower maternal mortality and enhance the overall quality of maternal healthcare services [1]. Preeclampsia, a disease characterized by elevated blood pressure during pregnancy, is thought to afflict 2%–8% of births and is a leading cause of sickness and mortality for both the mother and the baby. Any moment during the third trimester of pregnancy can lead to the development of preeclampsia [2]. Pre-eclampsia significantly worsens the body's inclination for increased blood clotting. One of the most common blood problems during pregnancy is thrombocytopenia, which is characterized by a low platelet count. The incidence and severity of maternal thrombocytopenia can be influenced by the duration of the preeclampsia syndrome and the development of the underlying disease. Studies have shown that pregnant women frequently have lower platelet counts than non-pregnant women.

Prior research has discovered a strong correlation between thrombocytopenia levels and the severity of preeclampsia. The third trimester of pregnancy is commonly considered as the time when preeclampsia develops, despite the fact that several studies have not explicitly identified thrombocytopenia as a direct risk factor for its development [3]. More than half of women with preeclampsia have thrombocytopenia, which raises the possibility that these patients will experience additional clinical symptoms. Many studies have shown a significant relationship between the severity of preeclampsia and the degree of thrombocytopenia, highlighting the importance of constantly monitoring platelet counts in these cases [4], [5]. The primary objective of the current study was to compare the platelet levels during labor between individuals with preeclampsia and those who did not have the condition. By comparing platelet counts in laboring women with and without preeclampsia, this study aims to shed light on the association between thrombocytopenia and the severity of preeclampsia, enhancing our understanding of this complex medical condition.

Methods

The research unfolds as a prospective case series study that unfolded within the premises of Al Hasan AL Mujtaba teaching hospital, Karbala Iraq. and in Alfalluja teaching hospital. Alfalluja. Iraq from January 2021 to July 2022. An extensive evaluation was conducted to determine the eligibility of pregnant patients seeking care at an outpatient facility of a tertiary referral hospital for the current case-control research. Individuals of a similar age who tested negative for preeclampsia (PE) were allocated to the non-PE group Group B (n=60), whereas patients who tested positive for PE were assigned to the case cohort Group A (n=50). In order to compare and evaluate the platelet counts between the patients who were diagnosed with preeclampsia and the expectant mothers who were in the process of giving birth but did not exhibit any preeclamptic symptoms, a thorough evaluation was conducted. Thanks to their rigorous methods, the researchers were able to draw important conclusions on the relationship between platelet counts and preeclampsia in pregnant women. Patients admitted to the gynecological hospital who were able to determine whether or not they were complaining of preeclampsia were considered eligible participants in this study, regardless of their age or socioeconomic status. Exclusions from the study included patients with known thrombocytopenia-inducing medications, preeclampsia with normal platelet counts, diabetes, endocrine disorders, antiphospholipid antibody (APLA), thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura (TTP), systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), immune thrombocytopenia purpura (ITP), chronic hypertension, and patients with hematological conditions. The development of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as the consistency of data collection and analysis, ensured that the focus of the study was on pregnant patients with preeclampsia. The research study's data were categorized into three categories according to their characteristics. General and sociodemographic data, including age in years, population type (indigenous or immigrant), employment status (housewife or student), history of pre-existing hypertension, smoking status (yes or no), systolic and diastolic blood pressure (mmHg and mmHg), weight (in kg), and height (in cm), were collected in the first category. Among the biochemical markers analyzed in the second group were ALP (alkaline phosphatase), GOT (glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase), platelet count, serum creatinine levels, urine protein levels, blood urea levels, serum bilirubin levels, and GPT (glutamate pyruvate transaminase). By carefully grouping the data, it becomes possible to examine every factor that might have an impact on the study's findings, providing a strong foundation for further investigation and analysis in the medical and healthcare fields. A greater understanding of the complex relationships between the variables under study is made possible by the rigorous categorization of the variables, which also improves the accuracy and reliability of the results. Many factors, including growth restrictions throughout pregnancy, stillbirths, and birth abnormalities, were examined in this study. The baby's weight in kilograms and whether or not they required admission to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) were also considered. In addition, the length of NICU hospitalization was one of the most significant factors under investigation. Thrombocytopenia, a condition characterized by low platelet counts, was divided into four groups based on platelet counts: normal ($150-400 \times 10^9/L$), mild ($100-149 \times 10^9/L$), moderate ($50-99 \times 10^9/L$), and severe ($<50 \times 10^9/L$). In addition, blood pressure measurements were separated into four groups: moderate ($150-159/100-109$ mmHg), severe ($\geq 160/\geq 110$ mmHg), mild ($140-149/90-99$ mmHg), and normal ($<140/90$ mmHg). [6]. Preeclampsia is a dangerous pregnancy complication that is diagnosed based on certain criteria, such as increased blood pressure (systolic ≥ 140 mm Hg or diastolic ≥ 90 mm Hg) after 20 weeks of gestation associated with proteinuria, which is defined as the presence of 0.3 g of protein in a 24-hour urine sample. [7]

Results:

Age, population, employment, and smoking habit were found to be similar between the preeclampsia patients' baseline data and those of age-matched non-preeclampsia controls by the study team. However, as evidenced by their diastolic blood pressure values of 104.85 ± 12.54 versus 62.10 ± 10.017 , with a

significance level of $P < 0.001$, and systolic blood pressure values of 170.33 ± 14.44 versus 102.59 ± 10.13 , those with preeclampsia had a higher prevalence of both past and current hypertension compared to their healthy counterparts. Furthermore, Table 1 demonstrates that, with a significance level of $P < 0.0001$, the BMI of the preeclampsia patients was higher than that of the healthy individuals (28.81 ± 5.417 versus 26.97 ± 3.83). The preeclampsia patients had significantly lower serum bilirubin levels (0.82 ± 0.27 versus 0.55 ± 0.27 , with a significance level of $P < 0.0001$) and platelet concentrations (259.64 ± 77.36 versus $198.85 \pm 66.71 \times 10^9/L$) when the biochemical parameters between the preeclampsia and healthy cohorts were compared.

Table 1: Baseline information of patients with preeclampsia was compared to that of healthy individuals.

Features of the patients (n=110)	F(%) for non-PE (n = 60)	PE (n=50) F(%)	P amount
Range of age: 15–43 years	30.10 ± 4.32	30.04 ± 6.66	0.950*
Occupation	Housewife/ (91.5)	(98.1)	0.209**
	Student (8.5)	(1.9)	
Preexisting Hypertension	Yes (0.0)	(100)	<0.0001**
	No (100)	(0.0)	
Smoking	Yes (25.4)	(41.8)	0.064**
	No (74.6)	(58.2)	
SBP in millimeters of mercury)	100.59 ± 10.13	170.33 ± 14.44	<0.0001*
SBP expressed in mercury millimeters)	70.10 ± 10.017	110.85 ± 12.54	<0.0001*
BMI	26.97 ± 3.83	28.81 ± 5.417	0.037*
Weight (kg)	173 ± 9.94	169 ± 14.41	0.186*

$P < 0.0001$ indicated statistical significance. Higher urine albumin levels were found in one group at 0.15 mg/dl and another at 2.24 ± 0.56 mg/L. Comparability between the study groups with PE and those in excellent health was observed in several metrics. For instance, blood urea levels were 32.76 ± 12.36 vs. 29.37 ± 6.51 mg/dl, with a P-value of 0.076. Similarly, GPT levels were 30.27 ± 43.12 versus 24.91 ± 7.24 IU/L, with a P-value of 0.367. Table 2 further reveals that the GOT levels were 25.13 ± 12.97 vs. 25.19 ± 6.82 IU/L, with a P-value of 0.975, and the ALP levels were 294.00 ± 79.38 vs. 291.62 ± 73.31 IU/L, with a P-value of 0.896.

Table 2: Comparison of biochemical markers in patients with preeclampsia and individuals without the condition.

Features of the patients (n=110)	PE-negative (n=60)	PE (counting fifty)	P amount *
Number of platelets (109/L)	262.64 ± 77.36	205.85 ± 66.71	<0.0001
Urine albumin (mg/dL)	1.02 ± 0.13	2.24 ± 0.56	<0.0001
Blood Urea (mg/dL)	28.37 ± 6.51	30.76 ± 12.36	0.076
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	0.706 ± 0.24	0.85 ± 0.24	0.002
GPT Units/L	24.91 ± 7.24	30.27 ± 43.12	0.367
Alkaloids of Phosphatase (IU/L)	291.62 ± 73.31	294.00 ± 79.38	0.896
GOT (L/IU)	25.19 ± 6.82	25.13 ± 12.97	0.975
Serum bilirubin level (mg/dL)	0.55 ± 0.15	0.82 ± 0.27	<0.0001

Only 1.5% of patients in the non-PE group and 87.1% of patients in the PE group, respectively, showed moderate thrombocytopenia when thrombocytopenia was compared between the study groups. Furthermore,

it was shown that only a small proportion of the PE group—3.6 percent—had normal, moderate, or severe thrombocytopenia. There was a significant difference in the incidence of thrombocytopenia between the PE and non-PE groups, with a P-value of less than 0.0001. According to Table 3, the total thrombocytopenia rate for all pregnancies was 6.1%, with 10.9% in the group that received PE and 1.7% in the group that did not get PE. Table 4 presents the pregnancy outcomes of women with preeclampsia (PE) and those who are healthy, as the study suggests. According to the study's findings, people with PE were more likely to need an emergency cesarean section (65.5% versus 11.9%, with a significance level of $P < 0.0001$) and to have problems from antepartum hemorrhage (APH) (67.3% versus 18.6%, with a significance level of $P < 0.0001$).

Table 3: The comparison of thrombocytopenia occurrence in patients with preeclampsia and those without preeclampsia.

Thrombocytopenia	Non-PE	PE	P value
Thrombocytopenia	1 (1.7)	6 (10.9)	0.041
Normal	58 (98.3)	49 (89.1)	
Mild	1 (1.7)	1 (1.8)	
Moderate	0 (0.0)	4 (7.3)	
Severe	0 (0.0)	1 (1.8)	

Furthermore, it was demonstrated that patients with PE had greater rates of moderate hypertension (20.0% against 0.0%), severe hypertension (69.1% versus 1.7%), and mild hypertension (9.1% compared 0.0%), respectively, at a significant level of $P < 0.0001$. Additionally, their newborns were more likely to require admission to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) (60.0% versus 35.6%, with a significance level of $P = 0.009$) as compared to babies given to healthy women. There were no appreciable variations in the study's pregnancy outcomes ($P = 0.310$) or baby birth weight ($P = 0.765$) between the two groups that were compared.

Discussion

The results of this experiment have shown that patients with PE had far lower platelet counts than the control group. In addition, it was noted that compared to the corresponding control groups, the PE patients and their newborns had a higher likelihood of developing problems. Through their ability to form plugs at sites of endothelial injury and their contribution to secondary hemostasis through the coagulation pathway, platelets play a critical role in the process of hemostasis [6]. be the outcome of a mix of the placenta's rapid platelet breakdown and dilutional effects. Although the majority of women have normal platelet counts, thrombocytopenia, or low platelet counts, can result from a drop in platelet numbers. [6] According to the research, the majority of thrombocytopenia instances found in the group with pulmonary embolism (PE) were moderately severe, whereas the non-PE groups had mildly severe cases (7.3% and 1.7% of cases, respectively). Previous research suggests that most cases of thrombocytopenia are moderate and usually do not have a substantial effect on the mother's or the fetus's health. However, thrombocytopenia can be fatal for the mother and the fetus in cases where it is a component of a complicated clinical condition [6]. It is commonly known that platelet counts often decline throughout pregnancy, especially in the latter trimester, when they might drop as much as 10% from baseline [7]. This decrease is thought to be essential to recognize that, given the severity of thrombocytopenia, occurrences of PE in this particular location may offer significant clinical circumstances. In this context, it is also crucial to examine how pregnancy affects thrombocytopenia and vice versa. The study's reported incidence of thrombocytopenia, which is 6.1%, is consistent with findings in the literature since thrombocytopenia impacts

Table 4: Results are compared between patients who experienced PE and those who did not after birth.

Features of the patients (n=110)		PE-negative (n=60)	PE (counting fifty)	P amount
Modes of Delivery	Surprising VD	(54.2)	(18.2)	<0.0001**
	Introduced	(15.3)	(9.1)	
	A planned cesarean section	(18.6)	(7.3)	
	Emergency caesarean delivery	(11.9)	(65.5)	
Complications	PPH	(71.2)		
	APH	(18.6)		
	No-complication	(10.2)		
High blood pressure	Typical	(98.3)	(1.8)	<0.0001***
	Mild hypertension	(0.0)	(9.1)	
	mild hypertension	(0.0)	(20.0)	
	extreme hypertension	(1.7)	(69.1)	
Results of pregnancy	Living	(93.2)	(92.7)	
	Stillbirth	(3.4)	0(0.0)	
	Growth limitation within the uterus	(0.0)	(3.6)	
	Unusual Behavior	(3.4)	(3.6)	

between 6 and 10% of expectant mothers worldwide. In the third trimester, 800 pregnant women in Karbala, Iraq had an 8.6% frequency of thrombocytopenia, according to a research by Jalal and Thanoon [8], [9]. In a similar vein, a third research study conducted in ALFalluja city found that thrombocytopenia was detected in 8% of the 150 pregnant participants, with a peak incidence occurring in the third trimester. [7] [7] In 73.8% of cases, the researchers found that the major cause was gestational thrombocytopenia; hypertensive diseases came in second at 23% and immune thrombocytopenic purpura at 4%. They found no evidence of any fetal or maternal problems during their research. According to the results of the present study, moderate thrombocytopenia was present in the majority of their cases [10]. This study's contribution to closing the current evidence gap in this specific area is one of its most noteworthy strengths. However, it is essential to recognize the inherent limits of the research. A case-control research may not always show a direct causal association, thus the results of the current investigation should be carefully evaluated in light of the study's design and participant selection. Moreover, extrapolating the findings to different settings throughout the nation is complicated by the fact that the patients were chosen from a single location. Because preeclampsia patients have a higher risk of problems than matched controls, especially if they have underlying medical concerns, it is imperative that they get specialist medical treatment prior to birth [11].

Conclusion:

According to the present study, those who have preeclampsia have higher levels of thrombocytopenia than people who do not have preeclampsia. Additionally, there is a higher likelihood that these individuals may have serious pregnancy difficulties, require emergency cesarean births, and have to admit their babies to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). It is important to remember that thrombocytopenia in preeclampsia patients may be a sign of poor outcomes for mothers and newborns, thus further study is needed to determine the best ways to reduce these risks.

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